

To Study the Effect of Shigaru-Neem Bidalaka in the Management of Blepharitis: A Case Study

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Abstract

Blepharitis is one of the most common diseases seen by the Ophthalmologist which is a chronic inflammation of the eye lid margins. It is often the underlying reason for eye discomfort redness etc. The term *Blepharitis* is made up of two words – ‘Blephar’ and ‘itis’ The word ‘blephar’ is derived from ‘Blepharon’ which means eyelid.¹ The word ‘itis’ is a suffix from Greek means inflammation. Blepharitis is ulcerative and non-ulcerative inflammation of hair follicles and glands along the edges of the eyelids. It is a sub-acute inflammation of the lid margins of the lid causing red irritant itch eyelids and formation of dandruff like scales on the eyelashes. It is a common eye disorder causing either bacteria or skin condition such as dandruff of scalp acne rosaceous can caused by general seborrhoea and staphylococcus but other pathogenic micro-organisms or secondary in infection may increase the severity of disease.² Bidalaka is one of the kriyakalapa mentioned in Ayurveda in which drugs are made into paste form and applied to the outer surface of the eyelid leaving the eyelash.³ In Bidalaka the tissue contact time is more and helps in the large absorption of drugs. The drugs having anti-infective and anti-inflammatory properties. Shigru and Neem is more useful in Netragata vyadhis. Shigru and Neem is Chakshushya easily available and more economical to patients. So I am going to study the effect of Shigru Neem Bidalaka as mentioned in Bhavaprakash.

Keywords: Blepharitis; Bidalaka; Kriyakalpa; Netraroga; Importance of Bidalaka

1. Introduction

Blepharitis is one of the most common diseases, which is a chronic inflammation of the eye lid margins. It is often the underlying reason for eye discomfort redness etc. The term *Blepharitis* is made up of two words – ‘Blephar’ and ‘itis’ The word ‘blephar’ is derived from ‘Blepharon’ which means eyelid. *Blepharitis* may be sub divided into anterior and posterior blepharitis. Clinically it can be divided into Bacterial Seborrhea or squamous, mixed staphylococcal with seborrhoeic, posterior blepharitis or meboimitis, parasitic blepharitis⁴

The use of therapeutic agents that reduce infection and inflammation is beneficial in the blepharitis. The uncertain aetiology and mechanism of the disease process make management difficult and recurrence is more, so for better management to avoid the recurrence of disease and more economical to the patient so the topic has been selected for the study.

2. Case report

- Name of patients- xyz
- Age/sex-32 years /Male

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- place- Nagpur
- occupation-private job

2.1. Chief complaints

- Itching over both eyelid
- Swelling over both eyelid
- Redness in both eye (on and off) .since 15 days

2.2. Present history

- No H/o any systemic disease or any major illness
- No H/o ay ocular surgery.

2.3. Ocular examination

Visual acuity of both eye is 6/6

2.4. Slit lamp examination

- Eyelid- scaling and lid edema present
- conjunctiva- mild congestion present
- cornea- clear and bright
- anterior chamber- normal depth
- iris- colour pattern normal
- pupil-normal size reacting to light
- lens- normal.

3. Treatment

- Bidalaka with Shigaru- Neem Churna.
- Dose- 2- 4 gram once a day for making paste.
- Time of applying Bidalaka – once a day in morning
- Durationof therapy- 7 days

4. Procedure

- *Poorva karma*

Preparation of patient: patient to be treated with Bidalaka should be placed in supine position and the part should be cleaned . The mrudu swedan will be given.

- *Pradhan karma-*

Shigaru and Neemb churna are made into paste form using sterile water and applied to outer surface of eyelids leaving the eyelashes.

1)-uttam -1/2angul, 2)-madhyam -1/3 angul, 3)-kanishta -1/4angul

Kala- 20 minutes.

- *Paschat karma-*

Eyes should be cleared by gently removing the applied paste with the help of wet cotton. Mrudu swedana is done with sterile cotton dipped into lukewarm water.

5. Drug properties

- Shigaru beej churna- Chakshushya, Krumighna.⁵
- Nimbachurna-kandughana, krimighana used for anti-infective action of drug.⁶

- The content of Bidalaka Shigru Neem is anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-Microbial, anti-oxidant, and anti-allergic, wound healing, analgesic and immunomodulatory action mentioned in Bhavaprakasha. The Pharmacological actions of Shigru Neem Bidalaka are like anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, blood purifier action, immune modulator action etc.

6. Bidalaka Importance

The Ayurvedic scientists Acharya Charaka and Acharya Vagbhata have mentioned about this therapy. They were aware of drug delivery through skin of eyelids. The skin of eyelid extremely thin, subcutaneous fat is very sparse and stratum corneum layer of skin which act as barrier is single layer in eye lid, so absorption of drugs through skin of eyelid will be very fast. In Bidalaka the paste of drug is left for 20 minutes so tissue contact time is more help in large absorption of drugs reduces the local temperature there by relieves inflammation, itching, imparting soothing effect and relieving pain, the drugs having anti-infective and anti-inflammatory properties, patient could get quick relief from symptoms.

7. Result

Table 1 Result of the treatment

Sr no	Symptoms and sign	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Lid collarettes Itching	Sever	Absent
2	a) Eyelid swelling b) F.B sensation	Moderate	Mild
3	Plugging of MG orifices	Plugging 23 to of orifaces	Clear orifice in the middle part of lower lid
4	Erythema	Moderate	Mild
5	Redness of eyelid and eye.	Moderate	Mild

Figure 1 Result of the treatment (Bidalaka)

8. Discussion

Kriyakalapa Bidalaka has significant effect in Blepharitis Bidalaka with above selected drugs provide anti-infective and anti-inflammatory effect. The tissue contact time of the drug is more so the large absorption of drugs take place therefore it providing quick relief in subsiding the symptoms. The Neemb Churna act as anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-Microbial, anti-oxidant, anti-allergic, wound healing, analgesic and immunomodulatory action. Pharmacological actions of Shigru Neem Bidalaka are like anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, blood purifier action, immune modulator action etc. so it help in reducing eyelid swelling, inflammation.

9. Conclusion

The study showed significant relief in the patients symptom therefore Bidalaka in one of the line of management for Blepharitis as per Ayurvedic science and helps to avoid recurrence of disease.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was taken . This is single case study .

10. References

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